

Tinnitus, What Could Make it Treatable, Case Review

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ABSTRACT

Tinnitus through orthodox treatment has minimal success. The well protected olivocochlear apparatus in a bony cage logically seems to make it difficult to find definite management. The use of alternative medicine particularly acupuncture has variable success. Acupuncture, effective for many aspects, may be useful particularly with the well documented myofascial trigger points associated with tinnitus. On the other hand, this paper described patients successfully treated with simple medications and herbs with or without acupuncture. This is followed with a review of 96 older adults over 50 years of age amongst 248 new patients during the year of 2019 in InteMed clinic. In these older adults, 20 had tinnitus and, discounting 9 transit patients not treated, the 11 patients treated had 9 of them (6/8 females and 3/3 males) with tinnitus totally remitted and 2 much relieved. None had acupuncture. What in our series successful to make tinnitus remitted are discussed. From the malleable sutures joining at the asterion just below the cochlear in the cranial cage, disorientating with mechanical stress and the herbs re-strengthening the body state through the myofascial support may have contributed to restore the state of the inner ear such that tinnitus could be improved.

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Keywords: Bottom-up tinnitus; Mechanical stress; Body state and Myofascial trigger points

HOW TINNITUS HAS BEEN VIEWED

Tinnitus as having sounds perceived even without external sound sources can be annoying. Patients with tinnitus, more common in women than men [1,2], may be associated with insomnia, anxiety, depression, decreased concentrating ability and disturbed quality of life [3], even with suicidal tendency [4]. Its pathophysiology has

been unclear [5], but often taken as a degenerative symptom since this chronic disease increases with age [2,6-8], obesity or long-term chronic disorders, though tinnitus is rarely associated with a serious medical problem [9]. There is no standardized treatment plan currently [10] as orthodox treatment are usually poorly effective [11], so that remedial therapies offered include drugs such as dopaminergic modulating medications [12], counseling and cognitive behavioral therapy [13] and acupuncture [14-18]. Most of these remedial therapies act by tuning the compensating disturbed neuro-endocrinal and autonomic nervous system [19-21] or relieving associated pain [22]. A review highlighted several studies for the role of autophagy in protecting sensory neural hair cells against oxidative stress-induced damage and suggested strategies to treat tinnitus by activating autophagy [23].

Tinnitus is a multifaceted symptom that may have many causes (otologic, neurological, metabolic, pharmacological, vascular, musculoskeletal and psychological). Several of these problems often occur in the same patient. Tinnitus may be the initial manifestation of several ear or systemic diseases. Tinnitus has been viewed as a functional disorder related to the complex network of the central and auditory systems [24]. While tinnitus is initiated primarily in the olivocochlear nucleus, it is often idiopathic with no distinct abnormality found. Nevertheless, it is often accompanied by hearing loss [25]. The odds ratio for tinnitus according to many factors were examined in 10,061 Koreans were – occupational noise (1.34), non-occupational noise (1.48), hearing impairment (2.27), chronic otitis media (1.53), chronic sinusitis (1.38), temporomandibular joint problem (1.69), depression (1.44) and stress (1.38) – highest in those with hearing impairment [26].

Essentially tinnitus may be peripheral or central in origin [23]. Many possible mechanisms were proposed long ago [27]. It is believed that tinnitus is driven by bottom-up or top-down mechanisms [9]. Bottom-up tinnitus related to hearing loss up and thought as auditory cortex related tinnitus and a parahippocampal cortex related tinnitus. The weakness of this model is that it cannot explain why some people without hearing loss develop tinnitus, whereas others with hearing loss do not develop tinnitus. The top-down of tinnitus has been associated with a deficient noise-cancelling mechanism, related to phantom generation ascribed to a change in the pregenual anterior cingulate cortex that corresponds to increased activity in the auditory cortex [28]. Notably phantom noise is multifarious while peripheral tinnitus noise is monotonous. Peripheral tinnitus at the cochlear level with no cause found is more common. Clinically, acoustic neuromas and head, neck and brain tumors can cause tinnitus and high blood pressure, atherosclerosis or malformations in blood vessels, especially those close to the ear, can alter blood flow and cause tinnitus. This need be excluded even by computer tomography particularly when tinnitus is unilateral.

Central origin is overestimated as the cause of tinnitus, as a recent study demonstrated no changes in central connectivity of auditory cortex or other key cortical regions [29]. As the source of tinnitus comes from the olivocochlear nucleus, healthcare providers cannot cure tinnitus but may help manage its impact. It is often bilateral but in patients older than 60 years of age, a study noted 50.30% had unilateral tinnitus, 36.97% bilateral tinnitus and 12.73% poorly localized tinnitus [30]. Data from 388 patients with chronic tinnitus in a tertiary tinnitus clinic interrogated, for the longitudinal trajectory of tinnitus characteristics, tinnitus distress, depression and quality of life, noted that 0.8% tinnitus could disappeared. A decrease in the Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI), Tinnitus Questionnaire (TQ) and numeric ratings for tinnitus severity, annoyance, unpleasantness and

discomfort was observed, but noted no differences in tinnitus characteristics, depression, quality of life or overall health status [31]. Total remission occurred in subjects whose tinnitus lasted for 49.0 ± 73.5 months [32]. Remission directly after treatment remains uncommon.

CASES OF TINNITUS IN INTEMED CLINIC

A few cases of tinnitus are first described, followed by a review of the cases in the clinic.

First case: Subacute Tinnitus

A young man (Y-21250) age 20 years, son of a well-off family, came in 2007 with on-off dizzy and bilateral tinnitus daily 4 months. There were no nasal problems, no aches and the 8hr-sleep and bowels were normal. He was studying in university for business and IT. He had dermatitis over the face and back for one year that remitted after treatment 3 years ago. Tinnitus was managed by ENT specialist with no help, MRI brain being normal.

In InteMed, he was treated with simple medicine and herbs. Dizziness was much reduced after 1 week. At the 5th week on treatment, it got transiently worse, ascribed to be related to sleeping late. Tinnitus was gone after 2 weeks, but at the 3rd week, it returned for 2 days with lethargy and headache. It disappeared but returned for 3 weeks again after the 6th week. Treatment continued with some varied herb combinations. He noted concentration better at 9th week from the start of treatment. At 13h week, tinnitus at day time is negligible, but still noticed at night. He stopped treatment, tinnitus continued in the next 2 years of university life. After graduation, he entered police force as his career following his uncle and tinnitus then totally remitted.

Second case: Remission and Recurrence, Associated Strained Ligaments

A lady (Y24903) aged 62 years old, a gynecologist, in 2015 January had unilateral tinnitus. The tinnitus over the right ear noised whole day and felt disturbing. Managed by ENT specialist, high tone deafness over the right ear was also noted. Her blood cholesterol was 7 umol/l., HbA1C 6.2%. MRI was normal and steroid 30mg daily was given for 7 days. The tinnitus stayed and disturbed her day and night. Retrospectively she had transient left tinnitus at high mountain top 15 years ago in October 2000.

After 2 months (2015.3.07), she came to InteMed clinic. She was noted also to have pain over left elbow and shoulder. Past health was good and bowels were normal. Examination was otherwise normal, though with detailed observation, both fifth fingers were mildly curved inwards. She was treated with simple medications and herbs with weekly follow-up. Being skeptical, she noted no improvement for the first four weeks. The 5th week seems slightly better and on the 6th week, the tinnitus was gone, both day and night. She stopped treatment then.

No problem for 8 months was noted, but she had tinnitus again, associated this time with dizziness and with rolling vision noticed for 2 weeks before. X-Ray neck, done for pressure tenderness at the neck, noted that vertebral width between C5-6 was narrowed. Treatment was given and tinnitus gone after 1 week. Treatment was continued for another 2 more months to strengthen her neck spondylosis. Tinnitus remitted for years.

Third case: Sudden Hearing Loss with Associated Tinnitus

A lady (Y23785), 54 years old has been well along, but had occasional headache and poor sleep when facing problems. She had once thyrotoxicosis 10 years before. Hypertension was well controlled on Betaloc 50 mg/d and blood cholesterol was 5.5 umol/l., LDL 3.09 umol/l. She noted in November 2022 difficult sleep entry as the right ear felt blocked with also some mild tinnitus. CT of brain noted bilateral mild periventricular hypodensities suggestive of small vessel disease, else normal. After one month, while sitting at 11pm, a sudden noise (sandy) came to the left ear and become unable to hear. The next day, she additionally had left ear pain associated with dizziness and nausea, while right ear hearing was also reduced. ENT specialist treated her with steroid, B12, trental, flunarizine, with no help. She came to InteMed Clinic wherein examination was normal except for tight left shoulders. Blood pressure was normal. Former therapies were stopped. She was treated with herbs (Figure1) and vit E 400 i.u. daily and polaramine nocte and acupuncture.

Hearing lost was bothersome. She slept well on the above treatment. Tinnitus and hearing gradually improved but hearing improvement were unacceptably slow (Table 1, Figure 2). After 3 months, antioxidants were added (daily CoQ10 100 mg, grape seed 200 mg, α-lipoic acid 300mg) but help for her felt change not obvious.

Figure 1: Herb combination at the early phase of therapy for the third case

Table 1: Course of tinnitus and hearing loss in the third case. Numbers made as subjective score by herself: 10 as the degree at the start. 1 as no tinnitus

Tinnitus	Start		Continued treatment			
		9-Nov-22	6-Dec-02	Jan, 2023	14-Feb-23	9-Jan-24
L Tinnitus	Nil 1	10	Noisy, sandy	8	4-5 (daytime) / night 1	2
Rt ear	Slight noise 2	Nil	-	-	-	Nil

L Hearing		Nil 1	10	8	6	3
R Hearing		Nil 1	8	4	2	2

Figure 2: Audiogram: some improvement, particularly obvious in left ear (though patient felt not satisfied as still disturbing)

After treatment, at the 6th month (July 2023), examination noted taut shoulders. With acupuncture for that area, she suddenly can start hearing clock clicking. Subsequently, she was advised to have Tuina every week and she felt help with definite and much better hearing after twice Tuina. With Tuina continued with help, she stopped acupuncture and continued just herbal treatment.

One year after treatment, she felt her whole body easier, better with hearing, even additionally able to hear voices better and eye floaties gone. One day on passing a forest, she started to be able to hear birds. Hearing continued to improve gradually. Body checkups all along satisfactory. Repeated CT brain scan was similar and showed no change. Tinnitus continued but reduced to mild 2/10 of initial tinnitus and hearing tests improved (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Audiometry tests showed improved hearing. Tinnitus then also much better

Review of cases in the clinic

After the above tinnitus case of 2022, a retrospective study of new cases coming to the clinic was done. Since the COVID times in 2019-2023 could have skewed the types of cases coming subsequently, the year 2019 was chosen for study as the latest typical year. Since the prevalence of tinnitus increase with age, the age of 50 was selected for the present study as the older adults' cut off for definite age-increase in tinnitus [33].

There were overall 248 new cases consulting for various medical reasons. 26 patients had tinnitus, 96 patients were older adults over 50 years of age, comprising 71 females and 25 males. In these older adults, 20 patients with 13 females and 7 males had tinnitus (Table 2). Medicine given in InteMed included herbs, polaramine 2 mg. at night and vit E 400 mg as antioxidant. All did not have any acupuncture.

Table 2: InteMed Clinic - 2019, new patients total 248 (167 female and 81 male). 95 were older adults aged over 50 years and 20 had tinnitus

2019 New patients	Age	Female Total 167	No Tinnitus	Tinnitus	Male Total 81	No Tinnitus	Tinnitus
Older adult:96 Tinnitus:20	>51age	71	58	13(18.3%)	25	18	7 (28.0%)
Young adult:80 Tinnitis: 6	31-50	50	47	3 (6.0%)	30	27	3 (10.0%)
	17-30	26	-	-	11	-	-
	<16	20	-	-	15	-	-

The patients at consultation were examined fully and also assessed for body state [34] with an objective body snug chart, from which the body state score was estimated [34] form and state (An example is shown in (Figure 4)).

body state score in the 95 older adult patients with or without tinnitus varies from 0-5.

27 NOV 2019

Snuag Chart 07

Date				
Swell	- t T+ / P	u-lip edge	4/4	
		Lip upper		
		Lip lower		
	- e E+ E++ / p	l-lip edge	2/2	
		naibed		
Sediment	finger tip			
	w b B B+	d-it	2	
		mg		
		p-it	2	
		ip		
		knuckle		
		obrium		
FACE		Conjunctival		
	w b B B+	Periorbital	2	
		check		
	- + + + + + +	MALAR		
		Malar Swell		
Perfuse face		intercanthus		
	w gy/gn d D	perinassal n	2/2	
		perioral o		
		check		
Bloat face		parietal		
	- b B B+	check		
		chin		
		(jaw)	2	
FINGER		tip	2	
		ip		
		dorsum		
Wrinkle finger		tip		
	- r R R+	mg		
		ip		
MESH		d-it		
	- m M + + +	p-it		
		mg		
- d D : nos/hnd		Finger	2 x 1	
		Submalar		
- d D				
NAIL	edt	W Moon	2/16	
	n + + +	White spots		
		Ridges		
	Nail	nail colour	2/2/1	
Tendons	e E			
	hurt - h H	n A		
	tight - + + +	n N	2/2	
		k K		
Dark/Red spots		face	2/2	
	- s m l M	neck	2/2	
		chest	2/2	
		forearm	2/2	

S :
body form collapsed

B :
blood stasis

Figure 4: One sample objective chart for body state. The swelling in and around the lips, the bloatedness of face and fingers, the darkish sediment around eye and fingers, the nail condition, the wrinkling of finger joints and tenderness at big joints, are assessed by degrees. Circulation stasis notable as bruisy dark spots and patches (B) were marked as blood stasis by their amounts and sites. Body physically inadequate with collapsed face or fingers (S), not related to wasting, were recorded

During retrospective analysis, all older adult patients, with or without tinnitus, were reviewed for the presence of dizziness or vertigo, pains and site, comorbid conditions and body state score. For those with tinnitus, additionally the side tinnitus, associated hearing loss and duration of tinnitus, were reviewed (Table 3).

13 of the 71 older adult females had tinnitus and was bilateral in 10/13 cases. 7 of the 25 older adult males had tinnitus and was bilateral in 6/7 cases. Dizziness and vertigo were not present in older adult males. In older adult females, 3/58 cases with no tinnitus and 2/13 cases with tinnitus had dizziness. No cases with no tinnitus and 1/13 cases with tinnitus had vertigo. It appears that dizziness and vertigo were more common in female older adults when having tinnitus. Similarly, pains and aches were also more common in female older adults with tinnitus (61.5% females vs 41.4% with no tinnitus). Yet again, in older males with or with no tinnitus, the association of pain with tinnitus is not remarkable. For comorbidities, both older female and male adults with tinnitus have more morbid conditions than those with no tinnitus (53.8% and 71.4% vs 32.7% and 44.4%); and these include hypertension, proteinuria, gastric acid reflux, nephritis, mood problems, insomnia, dermatitis, multiple aches, menorrhagia, lung carcinoma (and in those with no tinnitus, additionally, diabetes, osteoarthritis, stiff fingers, myasthenia gravis, multinodular goiter, prostate cancer, breast cancer, colon cancer, myeloma, gallstone, Behcet's syndrome and uterine prolapse).

Body state changes as well as pains and comorbidities in older adults were common. However, there were

obviously more body state changes in female and male older adults with tinnitus (85.7% and 100%) than without tinnitus (66.2% and 33.3%). Circulation stasis manifesting as bruise dark spots and patches were also more common in female older adults with tinnitus (46.2% vs 31.0% when no tinnitus) and body form more frequently collapsed (2/13 sunk with tinnitus vs 3/58 with no tinnitus). In male older adults, circulation stasis was also more common in those with tinnitus (71.4% vs 44.4% when no tinnitus) (Table 3).

Table 3: Analyses of the older adults over 50 years old among the 248 new cases. 58 female and 18 males had no tinnitus, while 20 patients - 13 (18.3%) older female and 7 (28.0%) older male - had tinnitus. Those with tinnitus had more pains and comorbidities as well as body state changes. After InteMed treatment, a high proportion remitted. (NA: transit patients who were not treated).

Associated Body problem	Female >51 Age			Male >51 Age		
	No Tinnitus	With Tinnitus	Tinnitus After Treatment	No Tinnitus	With Tinnitus	Tinnitus After Treatment
Tinnitus at presentation and results	58	13	6/8 tinnitus gone	18	7	3/3 tinnitus gone
		(10 bilateral)	2/8 ↓↓		(6 bilateral)	4 NA
		3 unilateral)	5 NA		1 unilateral)	
Dizziness (d)	3	2	2/2 remitted	0	0	
Vertigo (v)	0	1	1/1 ↓↓ in 3wk	0	0	
Pains...	24 (41.4%)	8 (61.5%) v		8 (44.4%)	3 (42.8%)	
CoMorbidity	19 (32.7%)	7 (53.8%) v		8 (44.4%)	5 (71.4%) v	
Body State changes >1	39 (67.2%)	12 (85.7%)v		17 (33.3%)	7 (100%)v	
Body State changes >2	19 (32.7%)	4 (30.8%)		3 (67.2%)	4 (57.1%)	
^B: blood stasis	^ 18 (31.0%)	^ 6 (46.2%)vv		^ 8 (44.4%)	^ 5 (71.4%)	
^S: sunk	^ 3 (5.1%)	^ 2 (15.3%)		^ 1	^ 0	

DISCUSSION

The older adults with tinnitus had more pains and comorbidities as well as body state changes. Poor body state with circulation stasis or blood stasis [35,36], more common in female older adults with tinnitus, just reduce the perfusion more as another type of poor body state.

The success of treatment in this study has been cumulatively better as noted from previous years of effective treatment in the clinic. Through strengthening the body state, 11 patients treated in that year had 9 of them (6/8 Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ) 2025 | Volume 4 | Issue 1

females and 3/3 males) with tinnitus totally remitted and 2 much relieved, even without acupuncture. Figures for older males with tinnitus may be too small in numbers to be significant for comparative estimation. The comparative results in females are more striking. Nevertheless, the success of treatment is uncommon in other reports.

In general, the success of orthodox treatments is minimal. The use of alternative medicine particularly acupuncture has variable success in many reports [14-18,37]. On the other hand, there have been fewer reports of treatment with herbs. One 1992 reported successful herbal treatments of 38 patients with 9+22/38 remitted or improved [38]. Tinnitus has been viewed in Chinese medicine as being related to body inadequacies [39], particularly Zang Kidney insufficiency. However, such herbs alone are not adequate and need combining other herbs to work more effectively. A comparison of herbal remedies over the use of carbamazepine was studied and described good results [40]. Although various Chinese herbal medicine formulae have been used to treat tinnitus in East Asia, none of them was supported by sound clinical evidence. Current evidence on herbal medicines for tinnitus is overall of insufficient quality and the conclusions from existing trials are conflicting [41]. Combined use of herbs and acupuncture is believed as probably more successful [42]. Older age tends to have a poor prognosis [43].

What makes it treatable with the alternative approach

Intermittent short time use of cervical collar (CC) appeared effective for tinnitus in his own personal case for a head of department of psychiatry and psychotherapy, as his painful cervical syndrome (CPS) with varying comorbid symptoms mainly tinnitus and vertigo, responded only partially to established treatments (physiotherapy, massage, posture control, exercise). Magnetic resonance (MR) imaging of the cervical spine was normal. Yet it was relieved after intermittent short time use of CC with complete remission from all symptoms within 3 months and stable over 10 years without further appliances except for occasional use of CC (about three times a year) [44]. He was more convinced when observing his acoustics technician's non-pulsatile tinnitus that started with painful CPS which 20 years ago was well treated, but the tinnitus remained therapy resistant even through tinnitus specialists over the years. Yet the tinnitus completely disappeared within 4 weeks by wearing the CC. It was attributed to upper posterior cervical muscle groups by repeatedly positive provocation with posturing and checked unrelated to reduction in vertebral arterial blood flow.

Cervicogenic problems may cause headache, dizziness and vertigo. Cervicogenic headache is a chronic headache arises from the atlanto-occipital and upper cervical joints and is perceived in one or more regions of the head and/or face. The pain resolves within three months after successful treatment of the causative disorder or lesion (by injection into lateral atlantoaxial joint intra-articularly; or into the arthritic C2-3 facet joint; or cervical epidural steroid injection) [45].

Cervicogenic dizziness with neck pain and dizziness, seen more commonly in people with severe head trauma or cervical spondylosis, can be vertiginous with visual problems, nausea and lack of coordination. The cervicogenic vertigo can be treatable and remit with physical therapy and inner ear exercises (vestibular rehabilitation exercises) and muscle relaxants that reduce neck tightness.

Muscle tension is notable in tinnitus when it is associated with teeth grinding [46]. The association between tinnitus and myofascial trigger points (MTP) is well documented [47-49]. For cervicogenic tinnitus [50], an editorial remarked that “The anatomical and functional associations between the ear, head, temporomandibular joint and neck are well known and are the origin of a very common subgroup of tinnitus (somatosensory)” [51], increasing nowadays with the home office and deranged postures. Tension of the upper posterior cervical musculature thought to be in conjunction with other psychological/psychosomatic triggers to cause tinnitus along the model of somatosensory tinnitus [52].

MTPs are small hypersensitive areas in palpable taut bands of skeletal muscles found in patients with the myofascial pain syndrome where stimulation of MTPs causes local and referred pain. MTPs in head, neck and shoulder girdle were strongly correlated with tinnitus and the worst tinnitus was referred to the side that had the most MTPs [53]. In 56% of patients with tinnitus and MTPs, the tinnitus could be modulated by applying digital compression of such points, mainly those of the masseter muscle.

What in our series of cases treated could make tinnitus remitted

The olivocochlear apparatus of the inner ear in a bony cage should be well protected from external inflictions except those in the neural substrate and channels. Tinnitus has thus been attributed to nothing but neural or vascular issues. For the same reason, the apparatus should be resistant to external manipulation for the sake of management.

The understanding of success in the current cases is based on degeneracy that set in with age and general morbid problems with possible related oxidative stress-induced damage [23], as well as myofascial tension unto the inner ear apparatus with effective treatment for sustaining the muscles and improving sleep in depth and duration. Additional herbs that act on neural recovery was used only in the treatment of the third case with hearing loss initially, while later stages recovery was mainly by body state improvements and muscle relaxation and strengthening. Notably the body state scores in the reviewed series were worse in patients with tinnitus than those without tinnitus. The essence of InteMed management is comprehensively working on the four aspects of the patient: local disease, general disease, body state (especially if wrecked) and the fascial formation/derangements, specifically and generally [34]. The fascia components are related and contribute to neural output and perfusion processes [54,55]. Any solidly genuine cause, the local problem, the triggering issues or the body state could all have contributed and affect the treatment outcome when degeneracy is the problem. Degeneracy is well conceived since this chronic disease increases with age [2,6-8], long-term chronic disorders, comorbidities and poorer body state. Tinnitus-related distress as well as unrelieved degeneracy problems raise a burden to mount up experience to various mental distress [56]. By this approach, the cause, the impact and the systemic whole of the multivarious cause-effect relationships from entire system of subsystems are managed.

Notably, the inner ear could be under mechanical stress. The anatomic dimensions and the variable distance of the inner ear structures [57,64], including the internal auditory canal (IAC), the posterior semicircular canal, vestibule and common crus [57,62,65] was well studied. Within the cranial cavity, the internal auditory canal (IAC), with its short (1 cm) bony canal within the petrous portion of the temporal bone, opens near its posterior surface. The head

of the malleous ossicle in the middle ear, the short crus of incus, the utricle within the vestibule of the bony labyrinth and the posterior semicircular canal are here in close proximity. The Eustachian tube, starting here from the middle ear down to the nasopharynx, has well-known changes in increasing vertical slant during maturation. Its 1.2cm bony portion may be considered part of the protympanum, starting below the tensor tympani muscle and gradually narrowing to end at the angle formed by the junction of squamous and petrous portions of the temporal bone [66]. These dimensions and slant would change during maturation. Similarly, the facial bones (Figure 5) are re-shaped with vertical lengthening and after maturity, the drop of facial components is still notable with visible complexion changes. With poor body state, it becomes even more difficult to sustain against the mechanical stresses. With stress, the bone fissures which are only relatively fixed, could be moulded in long term mechanical pulls, particularly at lower ends [34,67]. The asterion, as a meeting point of bones, joining of the lambdoid, parietomastoid and occipitomastoid sutures, is quite zigzagging and particularly have variations in its formation (Figure 6) suggesting how stress-yielding could be common.

Figure 5: Vertical lengthening of facial bones

Figure 6: The asterion, as a meeting point of bones, has its joining sutures quite zigzagging. It also have variations in its formation. Mechanical stress yielding possible

The cochlea as the origin of tinnitus is at the lower end in the inner ear osseous labyrinth inside the petrous temporal bone (Figure 7), communicating to the vestibule postero-superiorly, also situated close to the upper end of the Eustachian tube. The fissures at the asterion underneath the bones may realigned at the varying mechanical forces. Notably, the strong association of tinnitus with temporomandibular joint (TMJ) disorders [68] could be simply manifestation from the same myofascial-joint shifts. Shifting at the lower end is close to the sigmoid sinus (Figure 7) and circulation stasis could contribute.

Figure 7: The temporal bone with the inner and middle ear depicted in two layers diagrammatically. The cochlear not in the diagram is below the semicircular cannals and hidden in the second layer

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Illustrated above, the inner ear could be under mechanical stress with tinnitus manifesting as being sensitive to mechanical stress and hearing loss as a further sign of degeneracy. All these need to be further studied systematically. From the malleable sutures joining at the asterion just below the cochlear in the cranial cage,

disorientating with mechanical stress and the herbs re-strengthening the body state through the myofascial support may have contributed to restore the state of the inner ear such that tinnitus could be improved. With these considerations and the success of treatment on muscular and fascial tension points, it opens a way to manage tinnitus.

REFERENCES

1. Kim HJ, Lee HJ, An SY, et al. Analysis of the prevalence and associated risk factors of tinnitus in adults. *PLoS One*. 2015;10(5):e0127578.
2. Shargorodsky J, Curhan GC, Farwell WR. Prevalence and characteristics of tinnitus among US adults. *Am J Med*. 2010;123(8):711-718.
3. Ukaegbe OC orji FT, Ezeanolue BC, Akpeh JO, Okorafor IA. Tinnitus and Its Effect on the Quality of Life of Sufferers: A Nigerian Cohort Study. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2017;157(4):690-695.
4. Seo JH, Kang JM, Hwang SH, Han KD, Joo YH. Relationship between tinnitus and suicidal behaviour in Korean men and women: a cross-sectional study. *Clin Otolaryngol*. 2016;41(3):222-227.
5. Møller AR. Sensorineural Tinnitus: Its Pathology and Probable Therapies. *Int J Otolaryngol*. 2016;2016:2830157.
6. Martines F, Bentivegna D, Martines E, Sciacca V, Martinciglio G. Assessing audiological, pathophysiological and psychological variables in tinnitus patients with or without hearing loss. *Eur Arch Otorhinolaryngol*. 2010;267(11):1685-1693.
7. Henry JA, Dennis KC, Schechter MA. General review of tinnitus: prevalence, mechanisms, effects and management. *J Speech Lang Hear Res*. 2005;48:1204-1235.
8. Zagólski O. Management of tinnitus in patients with presbycusis. *Int Tinnitus J*. 2006;12:175-178
9. Yang SY, Liu H, Wang B, Zhang W, Zhao B. Research progress of idiopathic tinnitus. *Lin Chuang Er Bi Yan Hou Tou Jing Wai Ke Za Zhi* 2019;33(8):785-789.
10. Hoare DJ, Gander PE, Collins L, Smith S, Hall DA. Management of tinnitus in English NHS audiology departments: an evaluation of current practice. *J Eval Clin Pract*. 2012;18(2):326-334.
11. NIDCD. What Is Tinnitus? - Causes and Treatment.
12. Lopez-Gonzalez MA, Esteban-Ortega F. Tinnitus dopaminergic pathway. Ear noises treatment by dopamine modulation. *Med Hypotheses*. 2005;65(2):349-352.
13. Tunkel DE, Bauer CA, Sun GH, et al. Clinical practice guideline: tinnitus. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2014;151(2):1-40.
14. Park J, White AR, Ernst E. Efficacy of acupuncture as a treatment for tinnitus: a systematic review. *Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2000;126(4):489-492.
15. Choi JY, Lee DH, Choi TY, Lee MS, Ernst E. Acupuncture for the treatment of tinnitus: a systematic review of randomized clinical trials. *BMC Complement Altern Med*. 2012;17:12:97.
16. Rogha M, Rezvani M, Khodami AR. The effects of acupuncture on the inner ear originated tinnitus. *J Res Med Sci*. 2011;16(9):1217-1223.
17. Jeon SW, Kim KS, Nam HJ. Long-term effect of acupuncture for treatment of tinnitus: a randomized, patient- and assessor-blind, sham-acupuncture-controlled, pilot trial. *J Altern Complement Med*. 2012;18(7):693-699.

18. Doi MY, Tano SS, Schultz AR, Borges R, Marchiori LL. Effectiveness of acupuncture therapy as treatment for tinnitus: a randomized controlled trial. *Braz J Otorhinolaryngol*. 2016;82(4):458-465.
19. Choi EJ, Yun Y, Yoo S, Kim KS, Park JS, Choi I. Autonomic conditions in tinnitus and implications for Korean medicine. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2013;2013:402585.
20. Chrbolka P, Palúch Z, Hill M, Alušík Š. Circulating steroids negatively correlate with tinnitus. *Steroids*. 2017;123:37-42.
21. Aoki M, Wakaoka Y, Hayashi H, Nishihori T, Kuze B, Mizuta K, Ito Y. The relevance of hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenocortical axis-related hormones to the cochlear symptoms in Ménière's disease. *Int J Audiol*. 2011;50(12):897-904.
22. Ausland JH, Engdahl B, Oftedal B, Steingrímssdóttir ÓA, Nielsen CS, Hopstock LA, Johnsen M, Friberg O, Rosenvinge JH, Eggen AE, Krog NH. Tinnitus and associations with chronic pain: The population-based Tromsø Study (2015-2016). *PLoS One*. 2021;16(3):e0247880.
23. Vijayakumar KA, Cho GW, Maharajan N, Jang CH. A Review on Peripheral Tinnitus, Causes and Treatments from the Perspective of Autophagy. *Exp Neurobiol*. 2022;31(4):232-242.
24. Henry JA, Roberts LE, Caspary DM, Theodoroff SM, Salvi RJ. Underlying mechanisms of tinnitus: review and clinical implications. *J Am Acad Audiol*. 2014;25(1):5-22.
25. König O, Schaette R, Kempster R, Gross M. Course of hearing loss and occurrence of tinnitus. *Hear Res*. 2006;221(1-2):59-64.
26. Park RJ, Moon JD. Prevalence and risk factors of tinnitus: the Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2010-2011, a cross-sectional study. *Clin Otolaryngol*. 2014.
27. Han BI, Lee HW, Kim TY, Lim JS, Shin KS. Tinnitus: characteristics, causes, mechanisms and treatments. *J Clin Neurol*. 2009;5(1):11-19.
28. Vanneste S, Alsalman O, De Ridder D. Top-down and Bottom-up Regulated Auditory Phantom Perception. *J Neurosci*. 2019;39(2):364-378.
29. Wineland AM, Burton H, Piccirillo J. Functional connectivity networks in no bothersome tinnitus. *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg*. 2012;147(5):900-906.
30. Al-Swiahb J, Park SN. Characterization of tinnitus in different age groups: A retrospective review. *Noise Health*. 2016;18(83):214-219.
31. Simões JP, Neff PKA, Langguth B, Schlee W, Schecklmann M. The progression of chronic tinnitus over the years. *Sci Rep*. 2021;11(1):4162.
32. Sanchez TG, Valim CCA, Schlee W. Long-lasting total remission of tinnitus: A systematic collection of cases. *Prog Brain Res*. 2021;260:269-282.
33. Biswas R. Tinnitus prevalence in Europe: a multi-country cross-sectional population study. *Lancet Reg Health Eur*. 2021;12:100250.
34. Yu ECL. Body Form and Body State, Considered for a Fuller Clinical Framework. *J Altern Complement Integr Med*. 2022;8:287.
35. Park B, You S, Jung J, Lee JA, Yun KJ, Lee MS. Korean studies on blood stasis: an overview. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2015;2015:316872.

36. Tae-Young Choi, Ji Hee Jun, Bongki Park, Ju Ah Lee, Sooseong You, Jeeyoun Jung, Myeong Soo Lee. Concept of blood stasis in Chinese medical textbooks: A systematic review, *European Journal of Integrative Medicine*. 2016;8:158-164.
37. Tang M, Li Y, Lu M, Zhang T, Ge Y, Han J, Tang J, Chen Z. Efficacy and safety of acupuncture in the treatment of Meniere's disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Med (Lausanne)*. 2024;11:1463821.
38. Jiang S, Tao L. Audio awakening formula plus lidocaine applied to treat 38 cases of tinnitus and deafness, *Chinese Journal of Integrated Traditional and Chinese Medicine*. 1992;12(8):506-507.
39. Dharmananda S. Treatment of Tinnitus, Vertigo and Meniere's Disease with Chinese Herbs.
40. Zhang Q, Zheng R. Subjective tinnitus treated by a traditional Chinese medicine comparative analysis on 100 cases, *J Shanghai College of Traditional Chinese Medicine*. 1992.
41. Liu D, Hu Y, Wang D, et al. Herbal medicines in the treatment of tinnitus: An updated review. *Front. Pharmacol*. 2023;13:1037528
42. Shao Nian-fang. *The Treatment of Knotty Diseases with Chinese Acupuncture and Chinese Herbal Medicine*, Shandong Science and Technology Press. 1990.
43. Sun AH. A preliminary report on combined traditional Chinese and Western medicine in sensorineural hearing loss, *J Traditional Chinese Medicine*. 1982;2(3):215-222.
44. Bechter K, Wieland M, Hamann GF. Chronic Cervicogenic Tinnitus Rapidly Resolved by Intermittent Use of Cervical Collar. *Front Psychiatry*. 2016;7:43.
45. Goodman, C, Fuller, K. *Pathology: Implications for the Physical Therapist*. 3rd ed. St. Louis: Saunders Elsevier 2009.
46. Camparis CM, Formigoni G, Teixeira MJ, de SiqueiraJT. Clinical evaluation of tinnitus in patients with sleep bruxism: prevalence and characteristics. *J Oral Rehabil*. 2005;32(11):808-814.
47. Travell J. Temporomandibular joint pain referred from muscle of the head and neck. *J ProsthetDent*. 1960;10(4):745-763.
48. Eriksson M, Gustafsson S, Axelsson A. In: Tinnitus and trigger points: a randomized cross-over study. Reich GE, Vernon JA, editors. *Proceedings of the Fifth International Tinnitus Seminar*; Portland 1995: 81-83.
49. Bezerra Rocha CAC, Sanchez TG, Tesseroli de SiqueiraJT. Myofascial trigger points: a possible way of modulating tinnitus. *Audiol Neurootol*. 2008;13(3):153-160.
50. Michiels S, De Hertogh W, Truijten S, Van de HeyningP. Physical therapy treatment in patients suffering from cervicogenic somatic tinnitus: study protocol for a randomized controlled trial. *Trials*. 2014;15:297-302.
51. Mezzalira R. A journey through the tinnitus universe. *Braz J Otorhinolaryngol*. 2022;88(1):S1-S2.
52. Sanchez TG, Rocha CB. Diagnosis and management of somatosensory tinnitus: review article. *Clinics*. 2011;66(6):1089-1094.
53. Bezeerra Rocha CAC, Tanit Ganz Sanchez TG. Myofascial trigger points: another way of modulating tinnitus *Prog Brain Res*. 2007;166:209-214.
54. Yu ECL. From core and mantle to primary integrality - a brief introduction of the fit and snug states. *J Altern Complement Integr Med*. 2021;7:177.

55. Mazurek B, Böcking B, Dobel C, Rose M, Brüggemann P. Tinnitus and Influencing Comorbidities. *Laryngorhinootologie*. 2023;102:S50-S58.
56. Day JD, Kellogg JX, Fukushima T, Giannotta SL. Microsurgical anatomy of the inner surface of the petrous bone: Neuroradiological and morphometric analysis as an adjunct to the retrosigmoid transmeatal approach. *Neurosurgery*. 1994;34:1003-1008.
57. Djalilian HR, Thakkar KH, Hamidi S, Benson AG, Mafee MF. A study of middle cranial fossa anatomy and anatomic variations. *Ear Nose Throat J*. 2007;86(474):476-481.
58. Krombach GA, Boom MV, Martino ED, et al. Computed tomography of the inner ear: Size of anatomical structures in the normal temporal bone and in the temporal bone of patients with Menière's disease. *Eur. Radiol*. 2005;15:1505-1513.
59. Silverstein H, Norrell H, Smouha E and Haberkamp T. The singular canal: A valuable landmark in surgery of the internal auditory canal. *Otolaryngol. Head Neck Surg*. 1998;98:138-143.
60. Mutlu C, Govsa F, Unlu HH, Senyilmaz Y. The variational anatomy of the external aperture of the human vestibular aqueduct. *Surg Radiol Anat*. 1997;19:303-305.
61. Lang J. Clinical anatomy of the cerebellopontine angle and internal acoustic meatus. *Adv. Otorhinolaryngol*. 1984;34:8-24.
62. Muren C. The internal acoustic meatus Anatomic variations and relations to other temporal bone structures. *Acta Radiol Diagn (Stockh)*. 1986;27:505-512.
63. Amjad AH, Scheer AA, Rosenthal J. Human internal auditory canal. *Arch. Otolaryngol*. 1969;89:709-714.
64. Scerrati A, Lee JS, Zhang J, Ammirati M. Microsurgical anatomy of the internal acoustic meatus as seen using the retrosigmoid approach. *Otol Neurotol*. 2016;37:568-573.
65. Craig Hacking. Eustachian tube. *Radiology Reference Article. Radiopaedia*. 2022.
66. Yu mould Yu and Wong. Mouldability of the Body Core in Adaptive Form. *J Altern Complement Integr Med*. 2022;8:222.
67. Edvall NK, Gunan E, Genitsaridi E, et al. Impact of Temporomandibular Joint Complaints on Tinnitus-Related Distress. *Front Neurosci*. 2019;13:879.
68. Gómez Toledo V, Gutiérrez Farfán I, Verduzco-Mendoza A, Arch-Tirado E. Conditional probability analysis between tinnitus and comorbidities in patients attending the National Rehabilitation Institute-LGII in the period 2012-2013. *Cir Cir*. 2017;85(3):225-233.